

FACULTY WORK STRESS AND TEACHING PERFORMANCE AMONG THE SENIOR HIGH SCHOOL AND COLLEGE TEACHERS OF RVM SCHOOLS IN MISAMIS ORIENTAL

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ABSTRACT

Teachers are valuable human resources in the organization since they contribute greatly to its success. This study determined the influence of teachers' job stress on their teaching performance which covered mastery of the content, methodology, classroom management, and assessment. Employing a descriptive-correlational research design, the study involved forty-eight (48) college and senior high school teachers of RVM schools in Misamis Oriental. Descriptive statistics were used to organize the data on teachers' job stress in terms of workloads and working environment and teaching performance. Regression analysis was utilized to determine the significant influence of participants' job stress on their teaching performance. T-test was also used to determine the significant differences in the participants' teaching performance when grouped according to sex and work experience. Results show that teachers having reduced job stress have better teaching performance. Sex and work experience were found to be sources of variation in their job stress in terms of the work environment, but not in terms of their workload. The study's results indicate that job stress which is an inevitable phenomenon, can be handled and lessened to aid in achieving optimal teaching performance. Despite the unprecedented situation brought about by the Covid 19 pandemic, school administrators maintain control of the learning environment by protecting the health and safety of teachers in the workplace. As a result of their genuine concern and sincere assistance, they have experienced manageable workplace stress, which has greatly aided their teaching performance.

Keywords: *Job stress, teaching performance, workloads, working environment*

INTRODUCTION

The world has undergone a series of unprecedented complete or partial lockdowns due to the COVID-19 pandemic. This situation causes stress for people, particularly in the academic community, where stress has become a common problem for almost everyone to deal with. Teachers are much more vulnerable to higher degrees of stress (Reglin & Reitzammer, 2008) they now have to adapt to new teaching platforms as a way of providing education amidst the pandemic. This paradigm shift in the educational platform caused by the recent Covid-19 pandemic has added to the stresses and workloads experienced by faculty and staff who were already struggling to balance and juggle teaching, research, and service obligations (Houlden & Veletsianos, 2020). Teaching staff of all backgrounds and ages have had to prepare and deliver their classes from home with all the practical and technical challenges (Barbour *et al.*, 2020).

Recent research defines teacher stress as a significant imbalance between the resources available to educators and the high demands placed on them. This chronic disparity often leads to both physical and mental exhaustion, severely undermining their effectiveness in the classroom and potentially causing long-term burnout. Teachers are frequently overwhelmed by the combination of increased workload, classroom management pressures, and insufficient institutional support (Kern, Peggy, 2023). In addition, Agyapong *et al.* (April 24, 2023) study states that, teachers who are under stress or burnout frequently have negative effects that extend to students they instruct. To enhance teachers' capacity to manage stress, lower the risk of burnout, and enhance overall wellbeing, appropriate school-based interventions must be put into place. According to Carroll *et al.* (2020), understanding the sources of stress remains difficult due to the interaction of external and internal factors that have the potential to shape teachers' stress and resilience responses.

Teachers often face work-related stress because they are unable to meet the expected high levels of performance, resulting in an ineffective education and delays in national and global growth (Kyriacou & Chien, 2004).

Furthermore, due to the extreme diversity of teacher workplace environments in terms of the health-enhancing rule, it is necessary to identify the stressors that impact teacher performance at work, thus, the purpose of this study was to determine the influence of job stress on the teaching performance among faculty of RVM schools in Misamis Oriental. The findings of the study may have implications for developing a well-designed holistic program in coping with work stress.

The study looked into the participants' socio-demographic profile such as sex and work experience which can be a source of variation in their teaching performance. Sexes show different physical and mental reactions to stress. They approach stress management in very different ways, and they view their abilities to do so as well as the obstacles that stand in their way in very different ways. While women are more likely to report bodily symptoms linked with stress, they are also better at connecting with others in their life, which is vital to their stress management tactics at times (Stress in America, 2010).

Moreover, Podolsky *et al.* (2019) stated that teachers who work in a collaborative and supportive setting gain experience teaching in the same grade, subject, or location have a greater success rate, and more experienced teachers pass on their expertise to their colleagues. Also, the authors discovered that teaching experience increases throughout a teacher's career, and as teachers gain experience their students are more likely to perform well on performance indicators other than test scores.

Furthermore, job stress was found to be significantly related to teaching performance according to Greenberg *et al.* (2019). The study found that 46 percent of teachers experience significant daily stress which affects their health, sleep, quality of life, and teaching performance. During times when teachers are stressed, students' social adjustment and academic performance are also affected.

Dankade *et al.* (2016) also added that Vocational secondary school teachers experience high workplace stress as a result of work overload, huge class sizes, lack of enthusiasm, and student disciplinary problems which lead to poor job performance, anxiety, boredom, and frustration. However, teachers can be relieved of stress by changing the culture and approach to teaching through interventions at the organizational or individual level, or both. Mentorship, workplace wellness, social-emotional learning, and mindfulness have all been shown to promote teacher well-being.

One of the factors of job stress is workload. Raziq (2014) claimed that workload has a substantial impact on their perceptions of workload, balance, and job happiness. The teachers' perceptions of workload balance may have a major impact on teaching performance (Inegbedion *et al.*, 2020).

Another factor of job stress is the working environment, particularly in an online setting. Working from home has both advantages and disadvantages. The benefits of working from home include being more flexible in completing tasks, not having to adhere to office hours, not having to spend money on transportation or gasoline, being able to reduce stress levels by avoiding traffic jams from home to the office and having more free time. Job stress in terms of workload and working environment is hypothesized to have influenced teachers' performance. Teachers' performance was found to have a moderate and positive relationship with school effectiveness. Teachers' performance predicted school success; hence, teachers must be involved and work at a high level to overcome problems and achieve the school's basic goals at the desired level.

Mastery of the content is a variable under teaching performance. According to Olowoyeye *et al.* (2014), instructors' questioning behavior is not a major predictor of students' English language learning outcomes among senior secondary school students. He discovered that there is a positive relationship between the instructor's content mastery and student English language proficiency.

Another teaching performance variable identified in this study is the teaching method which refers to the strategies utilized by teachers to promote student learning. The disparities in the instructional styles and methods of the teacher promote significant

differences in their effectiveness and affect students' academic performance. Elvis *et al.* (2013) posited that the teacher-student collaborative technique is the most effective teaching method, followed by the student-centered method.

Classroom management is a vital factor for teaching performance. Study shows that teachers using an authoritative classroom management style make students anxious about their instructors' classroom management styles. Years of teaching experience contributed to differences in classroom management styles and the schools prioritize training classroom administrators in twenty-first-century classes, Gilbert (2019).

Furthermore, assessment is another variable under teaching performance. Derek & Elsevier (2011) defines assessment as getting to know one's students and their learning quality. The quality of evaluation is one of the most significant qualities of successful teaching. One has to ensure that students ask questions that require confirmation of understanding when developing evaluation tasks. It is also crucial to assess what students have learned using a variety of approaches. Consequently, the researchers looked at the relationship between assessment environment characteristics and student learning responses, as well as aspects of assessment environments that tend to be linked to positive learning responses.

Ultimately, in the school where the researcher is teaching, teachers are the important human resources of the organization as they play a major role in contributing to the success of the institution. To maintain high productivity and keep the teachers loyal to the organization, the management provides training, development programs, rewards, and promotion to motivate and satisfy their teachers. However, issues related to job stress and teaching performance of teachers continue to arise from time to time; hence, this study is hinged. Figure 1 shows the interplay of variables where job stress is assumed as the independent variable to have influenced the teachers' teaching performance which is the dependent variable in the study.

Figure 1. Schematic Presentation of the Interplay of Variables

Research Questions

The study aimed to determine the influence of job stress on job performance among tertiary teachers in RVM schools in Misamis Oriental. Specifically, this research answered the following questions:

1. What is the participants' level of job stress in terms of:
 - 1.1 Workload; and
 - 1.2 Working environment?
2. What is the participants' teaching performance in terms of:
 - 2.1 Mastery of Content;
 - 2.2 Methodology;
 - 2.3 Classroom Management; and
 - 2.4 Assessment?
3. Does the participants' job stress significantly influence their teaching performance?
4. Does the participants' job stress differ when grouped according to the variables of sex, and work experience?

METHODOLOGY

This study employed a descriptive-correlation approach to investigate the influence of job stress on their teaching performance as well as whether personal factors such as sex and work experience are sources of job stress variance. The survey comprised 48 senior high school and college faculty members from RVM schools in Misamis Oriental for the school year 2021-2022. The data were analyzed using descriptive statistics such as frequency, percentage, and means to describe the variables of the study. T-tests for paired samples were used to show differences in the participants' job performance when they were grouped by socio-demographics and hierarchical regression to determine the significant influence of participants' job stress on their teaching performance.

RESULTS AND DISCUSSION

This chapter presents data findings, analysis, and interpretation. The presentation follows the order and sequences outlined in Chapter 1. Additional explanations of the gathered information and inferences were also made to identify whether the theoretical assumptions of the study were confirmed by the actual data gathered.

**Problem 1: What is the participants' level of job stress in terms of:
1.1 Workload; and
1.2 Working environment?**

The frequency, percentage, and mean distribution of the participants' workload are shown in Table 1. The data show that the participants' level of job stress in terms of workload is low with an overall mean of 2.29. It means that the participants had a low level of stress in terms of their workload, implying that they were generally able to manage tasks and responsibilities at work.

Table 1. Frequency, Percentage, and Mean Distribution of the Participants' Job Stress (Work Load)

Range	Interpretation	Frequency	Percentage
3.50 – 4.00	High	0	0.00
2.50 – 3.49	Moderate	18	37.50
1.50 – 2.49	Low	30	62.50
1.00 – 1.49	Very Low	0	0.00
Total		48	100.0
Overall Mean			2.29
Interpretation			Low
SD			0.40

	Specific Indicators of Stress due to Work Load	M	Interpretation	SD
1	I'm not under a great deal of pressure at work.	2.25	Low	0.67
2	I don't work long shifts, overtime, or even on weekends.	2.63	Moderate	0.87
3	I am capable of meeting my job's requirements.	1.90	Low	0.42
4	I don't spend too much time at work, and my outside relationships don't suffer greatly.	2.46	Low	0.80
5	I am not overworked, and it is not difficult for me to focus on the task at hand.	2.38	Low	0.64
6	I feel tired during the day due to an excessive workload. *	2.48	Low	0.82
7	It's difficult for me to strike a balance between my job and other commitments.*	2.50	Moderate	0.71
8	I always get a good night's sleep without worrying about work.	2.52	Moderate	0.74

This is most likely to occur because part of the school's resilience and sustainability plan is adopting a schedule that would minimize the online contact hours not only of the students but the faculty as well. Instead of handling 4 to 5 classes every day, the teachers

more likely only have one to two classes a day giving them ample time to perform novel activities like learning more about interactive technology, module-making, online assessment tools and other teaching-learning preparations for online learning and distance education were among the major tasks of the teachers. As such, it is not surprising to note that more than thirty out of forty-eight participants or sixty-two percent (62.50%) of the participants self-reported their low level of stress as regards their workload.

The finding is in contrast to the result of the study of Jomuad *et al.* (2021). Teachers, according to their research, are vulnerable to stress and burnout as a result of long hours of teaching and a heavy workload. Teachers are overworked and their levels of stress and burnout are likewise high.

In terms of the specific indicators, the indicator on *meeting their job requirements* got the lowest mean ($M = 1.90$) implying their low level of stress as they cope with their tasks in school. It is also interesting to note that the participants admitted that they were under a great deal of pressure in their work ($M: 2.25$) which ranked second low among the indicators. This is a very positive sign because even if they were making adjustments in their instructional delivery, they were still able to cope with their preoccupations or workloads well.

The result of the study is also supported by the study of Amalu (2013). Positing that workload stress did not affect various variables such as co-curricular activity supervision, personal or professional traits, lesson presentation, use of instructional aides, student evaluation, and learning motivation.

The highest among the indicators was on *Not working overtime and even weekends* ($M=2.63$). This means that during the pandemic, the teachers under study were on a work at the home arrangement and were not asked to report even during weekends which explains the reason for the low rating on this indicator. It can be inferred that the high rating would mean a low level of stress as this was *reversely scored*. There is a clear indication that the participants were able to manage their workloads well.

Furthermore, the preceding conclusion contradicts the findings of Fan *et al.* (2017) which indicates that both workload and fatigue decrease teacher performance and that a high workload might lead to increased stress. The workload is one of the numerous predictors of stress and teachers' workload was discovered to be a factor that caused stress leading to a drop in performance. These finding were not confirmed in the study.

Table 2. Frequency, Percentage, and Mean Distribution of the Participants' Job Stress (Working Environment)

Range	Interpretation	Frequency	Percentage
3.50 – 4.00	High	1	2.08
2.50 – 3.49	Moderate	3	6.25
1.50 – 2.49	Low	39	81.25
1.00 – 1.49	Very Low	5	10.42

		Total	48	100.0
		Overall Mean	1.67	
		Interpretation	Low	
		SD	0.47	
Specific Indicators of Stress due to the Working Environment		M	Interpretation	SD
1	I gain personal growth by learning various skills in my work.	1.65	Low	0.56
2	My organization has a safe work environment	1.67	Low	0.63
3	My organization gives value to the spirituality of the workplace		Very Low	
		1.40	Low	0.61
4	I am valued and rewarded with the efforts I made.	1.98	Low	0.73
5	The institution extends help to their employees	1.67	Low	0.63
6	The management motivates me to go for further studies or career advancement.	1.65	Low	0.64
7	My job helps me to have a positive outlook on life.	1.67	Low	0.66
8	The management encourages me at work.	1.81	Low	0.61
9	I understand the importance of respect and the value of my colleagues.		Very Low	
		1.42		0.61
10	I am happy and content with my job.	1.81	Low	0.53

The frequency, percentage, and mean distribution of participants' stress levels in connection to their work environment are shown in Table 2. The overall mean of 1.67 stating *the institution extends help to their employees* suggested that their working environment was reasonably stress-free or that the teachers were experiencing a low degree of stress. This finding is indicative of the cohesive support from the school administration amidst the pandemic. The teachers may have received concern and genuine care from them by making their state of work highly conducive for them. This assumption is also supported by the large majority of the participants (81.25% or 39 out of 48) who reported having low stress in their working environment. Additionally, an acceptable learning environment provides comfort and relaxation for teachers, such as spacious offices and classrooms, which allow for specific learning activities and thereby reduce the danger of distraction for teachers (Edo & Nwosu, 2018).

Moreover, it is shown from the table that all items were rated low by the teachers, implying a manageable level of stress because the school organization has provisions to help them cope with their needs, such as giving value to spirituality in the workplace (M = 1.40); and understanding the importance of respect and value of colleagues (M = 1.42) which yielded the lowest ratings, implying a low level of stress in their working environment. This was followed by gaining personal growth by learning various skills (M= 1.65) and career advancement (M=1.65). These self-reports are favorable evidence that top management values spirituality, collegiality, and teacher professional development.

This finding is consistent with Hafeez *et al.* (2019)'s assertion that firms must maintain a better atmosphere to increase employee productivity.

Furthermore, the rest of the indicators in the working environment were reported as low connecting a generally highly favorable climate in the workplace as evidenced by their low stress. This finding aligns with the postulation of Hafeez *et al.* (2019), espousing that institutions must maintain a better environment to enhance teachers' productivity because teachers' performance and work environment are crucial.

Problem 2: What is the level of participants' teaching performance in terms of:

- 1.1 Mastery of content ;**
- 1.2 Methodology ;**
- 1.3 Classroom Management; and**
- 1.4 Assessment?**

The frequency, percentage, and mean distribution of the participants' mastery of content are shown in Table 3. The aggregate mean of 3.81 shows excellent teaching performance in terms of content mastery, implying that the participants had a thorough command of the content and were knowledgeable about their subjects.

As to the specific indicators, the highest mean are the indicators on facilitating the topics skillfully and spontaneously leading to self-learning (M = 3.90). This is followed by the indicator on clearly explaining the lessons (M = 3.88) and giving examples and illustrations on the topics (M=3.88). These findings denote the teachers' proficiency in making the lesson easy for the students.

Table 3: Frequency, Percentage and Mean Distribution of the Participant' Teaching Performance in terms of Mastery of Content

Range	Interpretation	Frequency	Percentage
4.50 – 5.00	Outstanding	7	14.58
3.50 – 4.49	Very Good	29	60.42
2.50 – 3.49	Moderate	11	22.92
1.50 – 2.49	Fair	1	2.08
1.00 – 1.49	Poor	0	0.00
Total		48	100.0
Overall Mean Interpretation		3.81 Very Good	
SD		.63	

	Specific Indicators of Mastery of content/subject matter	M	Interpretation	SD
1	clearly states the objectives/learning outcomes, structure, and plan for the lesson	3.77	Very Good	.750
2	explains lessons clearly and effectively	3.88	Very Good	.761
3	facilitates the discussions of the topics/subject matter spontaneously and skillfully leading to self-learning	3.90	Very Good	.627
4	gives specific and adequate examples or illustrations of the topics discussed	3.88	Very Good	.761
5	uses appropriate, varied, and relevant instructional materials to engage the students	3.65	Very Good	.729

It is worthwhile noting that all the indicators on mastery of content were all rated very good. More than 60 percent (60.42%) of the participants were rated very good in their mastery of content. This finding is supported by the study of Kamamia *et al.* (2014) which found that when a teacher can apply the subject content and students interpret the knowledge learned in class, the learners would be benefitted, and both students and teachers can contribute to positively changing their environment.

However, there is a good number of them (22.92%) who were rated as moderate. This finding calls for considerable attention on the end of the school administrators who are responsible for journeying with their respective faculty. The importance of teachers' mastery is also emphasized by Olowoyeye *et al.* (2014) citing the importance of topic mastery to develop students' competency.

Table 4 shows the frequency, percentage, and mean distribution of the participants' teaching performance in their Methodology.

Table 4: Frequency, Percentage and Mean Distribution of Teaching Performance in terms of Methodology

Range	Interpretation	Percentage
4.50 – 5.00	Outstanding	8.33
3.50 – 4.49	Very Good	50.00
2.50 – 3.49	Moderate	39.58
1.50 – 2.49	Fair	2.08
1.00 – 1.49	Poor	0.00
Total		100.00
Overall Mean		3.65
Interpretation		Very Good
SD		.58

Specific Indicators of Methodology	M	Interpretation	SD
1 use relevant and significant learning experiences that promote the attainment of learning outcomes	3.75	Very Good	.729
2 utilize varied online methods which include, but are not limited to their multiple intelligences and learning styles	3.56	Very Good	.681
3 apply critical/creative thinking, use collaborative and active engagement between and among students and between students and teacher to broaden the concepts of the lesson	3.56	Very Good	.711
4 integrate meaningfully and spontaneously within the subject contains the following: Values, Social realities, Other disciplines, Biblical text.	3.69	Very Good	.719
5 synthesize their learning	3.67	Very Good	.630

The overall mean of 3.65 indicates a very good rating in terms of methodology as revealed in the 50 percent of them who were assessed by their respective deans and coordinators *very good* in this area. This finding may connote that the participants were highly adept in facilitating learning most specifically in using relevant and significant learning experiences that promote the attainment of learning outcomes (M=3.75) described as very good and in Integrating meaningfully and spontaneously the following: Values, Social realities, Other disciplines, Biblical text within the subject (M = 3.69). The lowest among the indicators yet still described as very good was on applying critical or creative thinking, and using collaborative and active engagement between and among students and between students and teacher to broaden the concepts of the lesson (M = 3.56) and utilizing various online teaching methods (M-3.56).

As further gleaned on the table, there is a good number (39.58%) among them having a rating of moderate in teaching methodology implying the need for interventions to assist the teachers in designing effective teaching methods. This result finds consonance with the study of Isa *et al.* (2020) which revealed that most teaching methods employed by the teachers are essential on students' academic performance. As a result of these findings, the Student-Centered Method and the Teacher-Student Interactive Method were recommended to improve students' academic performance.

Table 5 below depicts the participants' Classroom Management frequency and percentage distribution. The aggregate mean of 3.79 indicates that the participants' ability to motivate their class to learn is very good in terms of classroom management. It is a common knowledge that teachers cannot get on with their main job of assisting learning unless students are in a ready-to-learn state.

Table 5: Frequency, Percentage and Mean Distribution of the Participants' Teaching Performance in terms of Classroom Management

Range	Interpretation	Frequency	Percentage
4.50 – 5.00	Outstanding	6	12.50
3.50 – 4.49	Very Good	28	58.33
2.50 – 3.49	Moderate	14	29.17
1.50 – 2.49	Fair	0	0.00
1.00 – 1.49	Poor	0	0.00
Total		48	100.0
Overall Mean Interpretation		3.79	
SD		Very Good	
		.57	

Specific Indicators of Classroom Management	M	Interpretation	SD
1 stimulates and maintains students' interest in the lesson (such as responding to their posts in the chat box, jam board, Mentimeter, or other applications; enforcing positive discipline)	3.88	Very Good	.703
2 clearly states the expected computer and technology literacy skills	3.75	Very Good	.601
3 uses tools that are varied, student-friendly, and promote interactive learning	3.75	Very Good	.668
4 states protocols for class participation and other forms of interaction	3.83	Very Good	.663
5 Informs students where and when they can avail of help in case of technical difficulties.	3.73	Very Good	.676

Moreover, as to the specific indicators, the highest mean are the indicators on stimulating students to learn (M = 3.88) followed by stating the protocols for classroom participation (M = 3.83). The new mode of delivery necessitates a significant degree of orientation in order for students to participate actively in online learning. It's worth noting that the participants gave the highest ratings to all indicators in classroom management.

According to Zainuddin and Hardiansyah (2023), with class management, teachers easily see and observe any progress or development made by students, particularly those classified as slow as well as facilitate the discussion of important issues raised in the classroom for future teaching improvement. The result of the study is supported by the study of Olowo *et al.* (2019) averring that classroom management characteristics of teachers (lesson plan, student discipline, teaching approach, instructional materials, and student assessment/evaluation) are crucial factors on student academic achievement. Teachers should frequently and adequately prepare for their lessons, use appropriate discipline approaches, use appropriate teaching methodologies

on a timely basis, use adequate instructional material, and assess or evaluate students in their classrooms during the teaching-learning process.

Table 6: Frequency, Percentage and Mean Distribution of the Participants' teaching performance in terms of Assessment

Range	Interpretation	F	%
4.50 – 5.00	Outstanding	5	10.42
3.50 – 4.49	Very Good	29	60.42
2.50 – 3.49	Moderate	13	27.08
1.50 – 2.49	Fair	1	2.08
1.00 – 1.49	Low	0	0.0
Total		48	100.0
Overall Mean		3.74	
Interpretation		Very Good	
SD		0.62	

	Specific Indicators of Assessment	M	Interpretation	SD
1	clearly aligns assessment to the learning outcomes/standards and seeks evidence to assess the attainment of these outcomes	3.73	Very Good	.676
2	Communicates expected students' performances and how these are measured.	3.77	Very Good	.750
3	gives purposeful, relevant, and meaningful homework/ assignments/ learning tasks	3.79	Very Good	.770
4	provides grading criteria or rubrics	3.73	Very Good	.706
5	provides clear, varied, constructive, and timely feedback on students' performance	3.67	Very Good	.724

Table 6 shows the frequency and percentage distribution of the participants' teaching methods in terms of giving assessments to the learners. The overall mean of 3.74 indicated a very good rating in terms of Assessment which is a very important component or element of learning. The majority of the participants (60.42%) had a very good rating on assessment.

Teachers benefit from assessment just as much as students do. Teachers can tell if their lessons are effective by assessing them regularly. Spanella *et al.* (2020) assert that teachers use assessment to ensure that students learn what they need to know to achieve the learning objectives of the course.

As to the specific indicators, the highest mean are the indicators on giving of relevant, purposeful, and meaningful assignments (M = 3.79) followed by the indicator on communicating expected students' performances and their measures (M = 3.77). These findings are indicative of the teachers' high cognizance of the need to have authentic performance tasks including the criteria for assessing these tasks. The element on

assessment is one of the trilogies of educational change which is a very important component of the learning process.

The indicator on clearly aligning assessment to the learning outcomes or standards and seeks evidence to assess the attainment of these outcomes ($M = 3.73$) got the lowest mean yet still described as very good. As observed by the researcher being one of the educators in the school organization, the area of alignment has been a concern among educators. However, according to the study of Toth & Csapo *et. al.* (2022) Findings indicate that evaluation programs force educators to adapt their methods; some do so in order to achieve significant improvements in student learning, while others adopt methods that actually worsen students' understanding in order to increase test results. Changes in instruction, such as the redistribution of coaching and enhancements in teaching, are brought about by pressure from inside the school (from colleagues and school officials) and teachers' attitudes toward assessments.

Problem 3: Does the participants' job stress significantly influence their teaching performance?

Ho₁: Job stress does not significantly influence the teacher's performance.

Table 7 presents the regression analysis of the influence of job stress on the participants' teaching performance. The result reveals that the whole model is significant ($F = 3.25$; $p = 0.048$) with only 8.7 percent of the variability of the participants' teaching performance as accounted for by the combination of the components of workload and working environment. This finding further implies that other factors such as coping skills especially during this unprecedented time, the creativity of teachers, support of administrators, and other factors may account for the remaining 91.3 percent of the variability in their teaching performance.

Moreover, the result shows that for every unit decrease in the participants' job stress in terms of workload, there is a corresponding .530 increase in their teaching performance ($B = -.530$, $t = -2.246$, $p = .019$) implying that once their job stress in terms of workload would be reduced, the more likely they would perform better in their teaching performance.

Table 7. Regression Analysis of the Influence of Job Stress on Teaching Performance

	Unstandardized Coefficients		Standardized Coefficients	t	Sig.
	B	Std. Error	Beta		
(Constant)	5.288	.668		7.916	.000
Workload	-.530	.218	-.379	-2.426*	.019
working environment	.075	.187	.063	.403	.689

Model Summary

R = 0.355 R² = 0.126 Adjusted R² = 0.087 F = 3.25* p = 0.048

Such a result is also supported by the study of Kurian and Varghese (2020) that teachers' performance is significantly affected by stress. The researcher believed that the study aids the appropriate agencies in better understanding the working environment and work roles of teachers as well as the different factors that contribute to their work-related stress and the influence of stress on their teaching performance.

Problem 4: Do the teachers' work stress significantly differ when grouped according to their demographic characteristics?

Ho₂: The teachers' job stress does not significantly differ when grouped according to their demographic profile.

The result of the test of difference on the participants' job stress considering the variables of sex and work experience is reflected in Table 8.

Table 8. Result of the Test of Difference in the Participants' Work Stress Considering their Demographics

WORK STRESS	Demographics		Mean	t value	P
Work Load	Sex	Male	3.40	1.93	0.60
		Female	3.19		
Working Environment	Sex	Male	2.84	2.46*	0.018
		Female	2.52		
Work Load	Work Experience	3 years and below	3.34	1.16	.251
		More than 3 years	3.21		
Working Environment	Work Experience	3 years and below	2.77	2.03*	.034
		More than 3 years	2.50		

*significant at 0.05 level

The hypothesis stating that there is no significant difference in the teachers' job stress in terms of work environment considering sex can be rejected. Male teachers (M=2.84) have higher stress levels as compared with their female counterparts (M=2.52). This may be attributed to the fact that female teachers are more open to expressing their emotions than male teachers. Female teachers in RVM schools have sufficient time to divert their stress by listening to music, actively participating in the school's wellness program such as Zumba after work, doing retreat and recollection, and expressing their feelings to their colleagues. Male teachers, on the other hand, see themselves as strong and may feel weak by showing their emotions and expressing their feelings to others. This is supported by the study of Kakada *et al.* (2018) on the job stress to the work environment of teachers. Their finding concurs that in private engineering schools, male faculty faced more stress than female faculty.

However, the result is in contrast to the study of Klapproth *et al.* (2020). Their results reveal that female teachers were more stressed than male teachers but the female teachers dealt with it more effectively. When external factors were considered to be barriers to distance teaching, female teachers used more functional coping techniques.

Furthermore, a significant difference is also detected between work environment and work experience. The participants with three years of experience and below ($M=2.50$) tend to have a higher level of job stress in terms of their work environment as compared with those teachers having more than three years ($M=2.77$). This is most likely because, when compared to teachers with less than three years of experience, teachers with more years of teaching experience were more familiar with the rigors and dynamics of teaching, particularly its routines.

The result of the study finds consonance with the finding of Chung *et al.* (2015) emphasizing work experience to have a strong positive association with performance. It is not just the amount of years employed but with the development of cognitive capacity as well as job ability. In this case, the null hypotheses can be rejected.

It is also worthwhile mentioning the variables of sex and work experience did not have a significant difference on the participants' job stress in terms of workload. As such, the null hypothesis cannot be rejected. These variables did not have a bearing on their job stress.

Conclusions

This study confirmed that job stress significantly influence teaching performance which can be accounted for by the combination of their job stress in terms of workload and working environment. The lower is their job stress in terms of workload, the higher is their teaching performance. A direct and positive relationship between job stress and teaching performance was also supported by the Person-Environment (P-E) Fit theory which emphasizes the importance of a person's interpretation of the environment as well as their relationship in shaping how the employees respond to work settings and events. On the other hand, the workload has been dominated by the Job Demand-Control (JDC) theory and its supplemented version which can also be employed as a strong support theory of stress in terms of workload to teaching performance. According to the P-E Fit theory or the Person-Environment (P-E) Fit theory that was established in partnership with them, stress is generated by a mismatch between a person's abilities, resources, and competencies on the one hand, and the expectations of the workplace on the other. Thus, job stress which is an inevitable phenomenon can be managed and reduced to help attain optimal teaching performance. Despite the unprecedented situation brought about by the Covid 19 pandemic, the schools can manage the learning environment by ensuring the health and safety of the teachers in the workplace. Such genuine concern and authentic support have led to the reduction of job stress in the workplace which has tremendously supported their teaching performance.

Recommendations

Based on the preceding findings and conclusions of the study, the following recommendations were drawn:

1. To the school administrators that they may:
 - 1.1 continue implementing the faculty's safety and wellness program which allows educators to keep a low level of job stress in the workplace while also managing their workload to maintain a high level of teaching performance, and continue the practice of showing genuine concern and support system as they journey with their teachers in enhancing their teaching performance.
 - 1.2 Explore differentiated growth or professional interventions for male and female faculty as well as the tenure or probationary faculty.
 2. To the teachers that they may:
 - 2.1 continue using their resources to manage their stress and performance at work to ensure a balance between the resources used by the teachers and the stress they are under to optimize their performance.; and
 - 2.2 Maintain their work-life balance for better service to the institution.
 3. To the future researchers that they:
 - 3.1 consider expanding the scope and coverage of the study in terms of a sample size to increase the generalizability of the findings of the study; and
 - 3.2 explore variables of role ambiguity and the resilience of faculty vis-à-vis their teaching performance.
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Compliance with Ethical Standards

CERTIFICATE OF APPROVAL ETHICAL CLEARANCE CERTIFICATE

Name of Researcher: KIMBERLIE A. LABITA

Approval Date: June 7, 2021 Approval of Expiry Date: June 7, 2022

The Lourdes College Research Ethics Committee (LCREC) reviewed the foregoing thesis proposal entitled Faculty Work Stress and Teaching Performance Among Tertiary Teachers of RVM Schools in Misamis Oriental and was found to be acceptable on ethical grounds.

The researcher has the responsibility for any other administrative or regulatory approvals that may pertain to this research and for ensuring that the authorized research is carried out according to the conditions outlined in the research protocol submitted for ethics review.

This Certificate of Approval is valid for the above time period.

Raquel A. Saab DM
LC REC Chairman

Sgd. Mr. Carl Nino Bondoc
LC REC Member

Sgd. Ms. Sara Zaragoza
LC REC Member

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